

FAIR 4 Research Software

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Software

- [SORSE](#)
- [Event Website](#)

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The software has become essential for research. To improve the Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse of research software, it is desirable to develop and apply a set of FAIR Guiding Principles for software. Application of the FAIR principles to software will continue to advance the aims of the open science movement. [The FAIR 4 Research Software Working Group](#) (FAIR4RS WG) [aims](#) to enable coordination of existing community-led discussions on how to define and apply FAIR principles to research software, and achieve adoption of these principles. The [FAIR4RS WG](#) is jointly convened as an RDA Working Group, [FORCE11](#) Working Group, and [Research Software Alliance \(ReSA\) Taskforce](#), in recognition of the importance of this work. Since July 2020, the group has been analysing existing work in this area and has started drafting community-agreed-upon FAIR principles for research software. This workshop will provide the following opportunities:

- Build skills in the development of principles and standards by contributing to the drafting of a set of FAIR principles relevant to research software.
- Understand the fundamental properties and uses of research software.
- Build new collaborations and engage with other RSEs and community members.
- Identify pathways to create (or synthesise existing work on) other elements of the application of FAIR to research software for future collaborations, such as the development of FAIR software indicators, maturity models, curriculums and competence centres.
- Consider how RSEs could play a critical role in advancing the FAIR for research software agenda, as early adopters, champions, case study contributors, and in ways that support regional/disciplinary RSE priorities.

The workshop will encourage collaboration around the drafting of FAIR for research software principles and will include progress updates on the four FAIR4RS [subgroups](#)